

TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT FLEXURAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: The three-point bending tests on constant strain rate(CSR) and fatigue loading under various strain rates and temperatures were carried out for honeycomb cored sandwich(SW) panel with GFRP surface sheets and Nomex honeycomb core. The maximum bending moments by CSR and fatigue loadings strongly depend on time and temperature and the time-temperature superposition principle for the storage modulus of matrix resin holds for the maximum bending moments by fatigue loading as well as CSR loading. Based on these results, the master curves of the bending moment by fatigue loading can be constructed and the long term fatigue life can be predicted using these master curves.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich panel(SW), Constant strain rate(CSR), Fatigue, Time-temperature dependence

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the mechanical behavior of polymer material possesses time and temperature dependence, viscoelastic properties, not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of FRP and its structures using polymer resins as matrices also depends on time and temperature even below T_g which is within the normal operating-temperature range.

The time-temperature dependence of constant strain rate(CSR), creep and fatigue strengths of various CFRP laminate has been studied by Miyano et al. [1-7] and McMurray et al [8]. It is observed by Enyama et al. [9] that the failure modes are almost identical under three types of loading over a wide range of time and temperature. The two hypotheses for these CFRP laminate have been validated: the same failure mechanism for CSR, creep and fatigue and the time-temperature superposition principle for CSR, and fatigue strengths. Therefore, the master curves of fatigue strength for these FRP can be obtained using test data.

In this paper, the time-temperature dependence of sandwich (SW) panel with GFRP surface layers and Nomex honeycomb core is experimentally studied. The three-point bending fatigue tests as well as CSR tests under various strain rates and temperatures are carried out for the SW panel, and the time-temperature dependence of flexural fatigue behavior of SW panel is discussed.

PREPARATION OF SPECIMEN

The SW panel consists of three main parts: two thin and stiff surfaces separated by a thick and light core. The surface sheet consists of four layers of satin woven glass fiber / epoxy prepreg, each layer is of 0.125 mm thick, resulting in total thickness of 0.4mm after processing. The volume fraction of fiber of the satin woven glass fiber/epoxy prepreg is about 57%. The core is NomexTM honeycomb used widely. The thickness of core is 24mm. The SW panel was manufactured by co-curing autoclave process under curing condition, shown in Fig.1.

The sandwich panel is cut by milling machine with a diamond-grit wheel under water cooling for testing. Fig.2 shows the configuration of SW panel and testing method. Both three point bending tests with constant strain rate (CSR) and fatigue loading were performed for SW sandwich panels.

Since the surface of sandwich panel is very thin, the transverse compressive fracture of surface sheet occurs at the central loading point. The surface sheet cures in the honeycomb core at the central loading point before the bending fracture. The steel plates were applied to both upper and lower surfaces for preventing this phenomena. The CSR tests were carried out using an Instron type testing machine under different temperatures and loading speeds. The fatigue test were carried out using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine under different temperatures and frequencies. Table 1 shows the testing conditions of CSR and fatigue loadings.

Fig.1 Molding condition of autoclave vacuum bagging for sandwich panel

Fig.2 Configuration of honeycomb cored sandwich panel and testing method

Table 1. CSR and fatigue test condition for SW panel

	Temperature T (°C)	CSR deflection rate V (mm/min)	Fatigue frequency f (Hz)
SW panel	25, 50, 75, 100, 125	0.02, 2, 200	2

EXPERIMENT RESULT

1. Master curve of storage modulus for GFRP laminates

The left side of Fig.3 shows the storage modulus E' versus time t for the GFRP laminate which is the surface sheet of SW panel, where time t is half of the inverse of frequency f , i.e. $1/(2f)$. The right side shows the master curve of E' which was constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t' until they overlapped each other, where t' is the reduced time to the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for the storage modulus of GFRP laminate of SW panel face sheet. The time temperature shift factor defined as t'/t is discussed later in Fig.6.

Fig.3 Master curve of storage modulus for GFRP laminate

2. Load-deflection curves and fracture behavior for SW panels and GFRP laminates

Load-deflection curves of SW panels on bending tests are shown in Fig.4. The load-deflection curves of SW panels are roughly linear until maximum load, and the loads drop suddenly at maximum load for all specimens. Both of maximum load and deflection decrease with increasing temperature.

3. Master curves of flexural strength for SW panels

The left side of Fig.5 shows the maximum bending moment M_{max} , versus time to failure t_s for SW panels at various temperatures T , where t_s is the time period from initial loading to maximum loading. The load components by the steel plates are deducted for the calculation of maximum bending moment M_{max} from the applied load. The master curve of M_{max} is constructed by shifting M_{max} at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t_s so that they overlap on M_{max} at the reference temperature T_0 or on each other to form a single smooth curve as shown in the right side of Fig.5. Since the smooth master curve of M_{max} is obtained, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for M_{max} .

Fig.4 Load-deflection curves for SW panels

Fig.5 Master curve of maximum bending moment for SW panels

4. Time-temperature shift factor

Figure 6 shows the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ obtained experimentally for the master curves of maximum bending moment M_{max} for SW panels. The shift factors are quantitatively in good agreement with Arrhenius' equation with two activation energies ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 ;

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K·mol)].

The dotted lines in Fig.6 show the $a_{T_0}(T)$ for the storage modulus E' of the GFRP laminate of surface sheet. The solid triangles show the $a_{T_0}(T)$ for the maximum bending moment M_{max} of SW panel. The $a_{T_0}(T)$ for E' and M_{max} agree well with each other at all temperatures tested. This fact indicates that the time and temperature dependence of the maximum bending moment of SW panels is controlled by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin. It is easily presumed from these results that the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin affects compressive fracture of SW panels.

5. Master curve of fatigue strength of SW panel

Based on above CSR test result of SW panel, the construction of master curves of fatigue strength become possible. The basis is that the time-temperature dependence of fatigue of SW panel is same with that of CSR of SW panel. We regard the fatigue bending moment M_f as a function of number of load cycles to failure N_f under the condition of frequency f , stress ratio R and temperature T . The functions can be described as $M_f(N_f, f, R, T)$. The CSR failure bending moment $M_f(t_f, T)$ is considered as fatigue bending moment at $N_f=1/2$ or $t_f=1/(2f)$, and $R=0$.

Fig.6 Time-temperature dependent shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ of SW panel

Figure 7 shows the fatigue bending moment M_f versus the number of load cycles to failure N_f at frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$ and stress ratio $R=0.05$. The CSR maximum bending moment is regarded as the fatigue failure load at $N_f=1/2$. The fatigue bending moment decreases with time, temperature and number of load cycles clearly.

The time-temperature shift factor obtained from CSR test is adopted to calculate the reduced time t_f' as well as reduced frequency f' , which are necessary to construct the fatigue bending moment master curves for the SW panel. The expression is as follows:

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T), \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (2)$$

According to Equation (2), the important alternative master curves can be gotten, depicted as $M_f(t_f'; f', T_0)$. Also, the master curves of $M_f(t_f'; N_f; T_0)$ can be constructed by connecting the points of the same number of load cycles to failure on these curves $M_f(t_f'; f', T_0)$.

Figure 8 shows the fatigue bending moment master curves at reference temperature $T=25^\circ\text{C}$, stress ratio $R=0.05$. The x-axis is the reduced time to failure t_f' in logarithmic scale, which is converted from N_f in Fig.7 by equation (2) and the CSR shifting factor. The master curves of fatigue bending moment of SW panel at fixed cycle number N_f are constructed by

Fig. 7 S-N curves of SW panel for frequency $f=2$ and stress ratio $R=0.05$ at various temperatures

Fig.8 Fatigue load versus number of cycles to failure at frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$, stress ratio $R=0.05$

connecting the points at f' curves with same N_f indicated by dotted line.

For the SW panel, under temperature $T=25^\circ\text{C}$, the fatigue bending moment is lower than the CSR maximum bending moment. Under temperature $T=75^\circ\text{C}$, the fatigue bending moment becomes very close to the CSR maximum bending moment. After temperature reaches $T=125^\circ\text{C}$, this reverse phenomena becomes more apparent with increase of number of load cycles to failure N_f . This inverse phenomena links with failure mode change when temperature approaches T_g , explained in later paragraph.

The validity of master curves for fatigue bending moment were checked by predicting the long term fatigue failure life. Fig.9 shows M_f-N_f curves at $f=0.02\text{Hz}$ predicted by using the master curves of Fig.8 and relevant experiment points under various temperatures. The comparison indicates that the predicted curves agrees well with the experiment points. It can be confirmed that the time-temperature superposition principle holds for the fatigue bending moment.

Fig.9 Fatigue load versus cycle number to failure at frequency $f=0.002\text{Hz}$, stress ratio $R=0.05$

6. CSR and fatigue failure mode

Figure 10 shows the fractographs of central loading point of SW panel after CSR and fatigue tests at different temperatures, the left side being CSR specimens and the right side being fatigue specimens. For both CSR and fatigue tests, all specimens failed at loading points of the compressive sides. At room temperature, the CSR specimen's failure is triggered by microbuckling. At high temperature, $T=125^\circ\text{C}$, the CSR specimen's failure is triggered by Euler's buckling of surface sheet.

Figure 11 shows the failure mode change of CSR and Fatigue test data on the master curves. From this figure, the failure mode can be seen more clearly with three regions. At low temperature or small reduced time, the failure is microbuckling. As the reduced time increases, i.e. near the glass transition temperature T_g , the mode changes to mixed mode. As the reduced time increase continuously, i.e. at high temperature, the failure mode becomes Euler's buckling. The change of failure mode from microbuckling to Euler's buckling corresponds clearly to the change of fatigue bending moment from decreasing to increasing with increasing number of load cycles to failure.

CONCLUSIONS

The three-point bending tests on constant strain rate (CSR) and fatigue loading under various strain rates and temperatures were carried out for honeycomb cored sandwich (SW) panel with GFRP surface sheets and Nomex honeycomb core. The maximum bending moments by CSR and fatigue loadings strongly depend on time and temperature and the time-temperature superposition principle for the storage modulus of matrix resin holds for the maximum bending moments by fatigue loading as well as CSR loading. Based on these results, the master curves of the bending moment by fatigue loading have been constructed and the long term fatigue life can be predicted using these master

curves. The fatigue bending moment decreases with time and temperature. The change of failure mode from microbuckling to Euler's buckling corresponds clearly to the change of fatigue bending moment from decreasing to increasing with increasing number of load cycles to failure.

Fig.10 Fractograph of CSR and fatigue test of SW panel at different temperatures

Fig.11 Change of failure modes of SW panel with reduced time

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